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Application of the Fenton and photo-Fenton processes in pharmaceutical removal: New perspectives in environmental protection

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ABSTRACT

Micropollutants are detected in all elements of the environment. Among them, pharmaceuticals are a large group. Advanced oxidation processes are a promising solution for their removal. In this study, the simultaneous removal of four pharmaceuticals (ibuprofen, diclofenac, carbamazepine, and sulfamethoxazole) from aqueous solutions was investigated using the Fenton and photo-Fenton processes. The experimental design used a "one-variable-at-a-time" approach to optimise key operating parameters, including exposure time, pH, hydrogen peroxide dosage, Fe²⁺ source, and H₂O₂:Fe²⁺ ratio. A batch reactor setup was used for all experiments. Optimal removal efficiencies were achieved at pH three and a H₂O₂ dosage of 7.3 mL/L. Photo-Fenton consistently outperformed the Fenton process, achieving complete degradation of sulfamethoxazole, carbamazepine, and ibuprofen within 10 min under optimised conditions. At lower ratios of H₂O₂ to Fe²⁺ (10:1, 20:1), removal efficiency approaches nearly 100 % for all pharmaceuticals when using FeSO₄·7H₂O. In contrast, the iron nanoparticles show reduced efficacy at these ratios. However, at higher ratios (25:1, 50:1, 75:1), the efficiency of reactions FeSO₄·7H₂O decreases and becomes comparable to that achieved with iron nanoparticles. These results highlight the potential of Fenton-based processes, combined with UV radiation and optimised reagent conditions, for the effective removal of pharmaceuticals from wastewater, paving the way for sustainable environmental remediation applications.

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1. Introduction

Pollution of the natural environment, including water resources and even drinking water, by micropollutants has become an increasingly urgent problem in recent years. Among the myriad of chemicals entering our environment, pharmaceuticals (PhCs) and their transformation products are particularly concerning and hazardous [1,2]. PhCs, which are biologically active substances, often after being expelled from the human body, still can interact with living cells and organisms in the environment. Even at low concentrations, they can alter cellular metabolic processes and cause toxic effects [3–5]. Consequently, PhCs have been recognized as significant environmental pollutants, classified as emerging contaminants (EC), with a particularly detrimental impact on aquatic and soil ecosystems. PhCs entering the environment originate from various sources, including substances excreted by humans and animals that end up in wastewater treatment systems, improper disposal of unused medicines, and agricultural runoff. Once in the environment, PhCs and their metabolites can persist due to their slow biotransformation, potentially disrupting the ecological balance and posing risks to wildlife and human health [6]. Conventional wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are not designed to remove effectively. While biological treatment methods, such as activated sludge processes, anaerobic/anaerobic/oxic systems, oxidation ditches or filters, are widely used for their cost-effectiveness and ability to degrade organic pollutants, they face significant limitations in addressing recalcitrant contaminants like PhCs and personal care products [7]. These contaminants often cause microbial degradation due to their complex chemical structures and high stability, allowing them to persist in the environment even after treatment. Furthermore, the efficiency of biological processes can be compromised by operational conditions, such as fluctuations in temperature, pH, and the presence of toxic substances, reducing their effectiveness across varying wastewater compositions [8,9]. The inadequacy of conventional treatments in meeting regulatory standards for ECs, especially pharmaceutical residues, is well-documented. Studies have shown that these methods typically achieve only partial removal of compounds such as ibuprofen, carbamazepine, and diclofenac, leaving substantial concentrations of these pollutants in treated effluents [10–14]. Therefore, PhCs resistant to treatment processes enter natural water bodies [15]. The efficiency of pharmaceutical removal efficiency (RE) depends on several factors. The main ones are the type of substance, its initial concentration, and the process used.

It should be noted that in the case of some substances, i.e., caffeine or paracetamol, the RE in a conventional WWTP may reach 100 %. In contrast, the RE is extremely low or even negatively harmful for substances resistant to traditional wastewater treatment processes. The negative removal (NR) rate is a complex issue. NR occurs when the detected concentration of a given substance is more significant in effluents than in influents. NR is a worldwide phenomenon, and many causes may be related to separation processes, conjugation–deconjugation, biotransformation, and leaching. The most common phenomenon (NR) is observed in the case of carbamazepine and some antibiotics, e.g., sulfamethoxazole [7,16]. Due to the insufficient effectiveness of traditional treatment methods, developing and implementing new techniques to enhance the removal efficiency of PhCs has become necessary. Methods available on the market include advanced oxidation processes (AOPs), adsorption, membrane processes such as ultrafiltration and nanofiltration, and reverse osmosis. Among them, AOPs aim to decompose these persistent pollutants using highly reactive radicals, offering the most promising solution for degrading organic contaminants. AOPs include ozonation, Fenton process, photocatalysis, UV-H₂O₂ treatment, ozone-H₂O₂, electrochemical oxidation, advanced persulfate oxidation, cold plasma treatment, and others [17, 18]. For example, TiO₂ photocatalysis has achieved 80 % removal of diclofenac in deionized water at 0.5 mg/L, while photocatalytic ozonation has demonstrated 91 % total organic carbon removal for carbamazepine in treated domestic wastewater [15]. Similarly, UV-H₂O₂

treatment removed over 90 % of norfloxacin within 2 h under optimal conditions, and catalytic ozonation achieved 86 % removal of 2,4,6-trichlorophenol in industrial wastewater [19,20]. Sulfate radical-based AOPs (SR-AOPs) have achieved 100 % degradation of sulfamethoxazole and pentachlorophenol using biochar and peroxydisulfate as catalysts. The Fenton and photo-Fenton processes, particularly, have garnered significant interest due to their effectiveness in generating hydroxyl radicals, which can oxidize a wide range of organic pollutants [15,21–26]. The classical Fenton process has demonstrated remarkable efficiency, achieving 100 % removal of phenolic compounds, 70 % chemical oxygen demand (COD) reduction, and 50 % total organic carbon (TOC) removal in hospital wastewater within 1 h under optimal acidic conditions [19]. Fenton-like processes, enhanced with chelating agents such as citric acid, have shown an average RE of 74 % for veterinary antibiotics, broadening the applicability to a broader pH range [27]. Innovative modifications, such as photoelectro-Fenton, further enhance performance, with total mineralization rates of 94–96 % achieved for flumequine in 6 h under controlled light and electrochemical conditions. Similarly, Fe(III)-chelate-assisted UV/persulfate systems have emerged as promising methods for sulfamethazine degradation, achieving 93.6–99.6 % removal at near-neutral pH without significant loss of efficiency across varying water matrices [28]. The use of heterogeneous electro-Fenton processes also addresses key drawbacks, such as the need for extensive pH adjustment and sludge production. For instance, ibuprofen degradation reached 97 % using ferric citrate-supported cathodes, with sustained performance over multiple cycles, and energy consumption was kept low at 0.24–2.65 kWh/log m³ depending on current density [29]. Such innovations highlight the practical applications and enhanced efficiency of Fenton-based processes, laying the groundwork for understanding the core reactions driving their pollutant degradation capabilities. The Fenton process involves the reaction of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) with iron(II) ions (Fe²⁺) to produce highly reactive hydroxyl radicals (•OH). Radicals can break down complex organic molecules into smaller, less harmful compounds and oxidize a wide range of organic pollutants. The following equations can represent the fundamental reactions in the Fenton process:

The efficiency of the Fenton process is highly dependent on several operating parameters. The optimal pH for the classical Fenton process is typically acidic (around 2.8–3.5), as this range stabilizes Fe²⁺ and enhances hydroxyl radical generation while higher pH values can result in precipitation of iron as ferric hydroxide, reducing catalyst availability. The dosages of H₂O₂ and Fe²⁺ also play critical roles, where excess oxidant can lead to scavenging of hydroxyl radicals, and insufficient catalyst limits reaction kinetics. Temperature influences the decomposition rate of H₂O₂ and the kinetics of radical generation, with higher temperatures generally increasing reaction efficiency but also potentially causing non-selective oxidation [30]. In turn, the photo-Fenton process, an extension of the traditional Fenton reaction, uses ultraviolet (UV) radiation to increase the production of hydroxyl radicals further and improve the degradation process's overall efficiency. In the photo-Fenton process, UV irradiation significantly enhances the degradation of pollutants by regenerating Fe²⁺ from Fe³⁺, thereby sustaining the catalytic cycle and increasing hydroxyl radical production [31]. This mechanism is particularly effective in treating complex and refractory organic pollutants. The interplay of these parameters is crucial for maximizing the process's efficiency while minimizing energy and chemical inputs. Eq. 4 shows a simplified notation of the photo-Fenton reaction.

In addition to the use of UV radiation, the Fenton process can be modified by using alternative iron sources, optimizing reaction conditions such as pH and temperature, employing continuous flow systems to enhance scalability, and combining it with other processes (e.g. electro-Fenton, Fenton process and ultrasound) [22,32–34]. These general modifications aim to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of pollutant degradation, making the process more versatile and adaptable for various environmental applications.

Modifications of the traditional Fenton and photo-Fenton processes, incorporating nanoparticles (NPs), offer significant potential for enhancing the removal of pharmaceutical contaminants [35]. These modifications leverage the unique properties of NPs, such as increased surface area and higher catalytic activity, leading to more efficient production of hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$) and consequently enhancing pollutant degradation [36]. The primary advantages of using NPs include enhanced efficiency due to a larger surface area and more active sites, which results in faster and more complete degradation of PhCs. Additionally, the high reactivity of NPs can reduce the need for excessive amounts of hydrogen peroxide and iron salts, making the process more cost-effective and environmentally friendly. NPs can also be tailored in size, shape, and surface modifications to optimize their performance for specific pollutants and reaction conditions. Incorporating NPs into Fenton and photo-Fenton processes presents a promising upgrade for pharmaceutical removal, offering enhanced efficiency and versatility while posing certain toxicity, stability, and cost challenges. Ongoing research and development are crucial to optimize these processes and address potential drawbacks.

This study explores the simultaneous removal of multiple PhCs using the Fenton and photo-Fenton processes. Four commonly used PhCs—ibuprofen (IBU), diclofenac (DCF), carbamazepine (CBZ), and sulfamethoxazole (SMX)—were selected for investigation due to their widespread use and frequent detection in environmental samples. DCF is a widely used non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) commonly found in surface water and wastewater effluents. It has been identified as a priority pollutant due to its toxicity to aquatic organisms, mainly fish and algae, and its potential to disrupt endocrine functions. Its high persistence and resistance to conventional treatment methods exacerbate its environmental impact [37–39]. IBU is another widely used NSAID, one of the most commonly detected pharmaceuticals in aquatic environments. While it is more biodegradable than some other compounds, its incomplete removal during wastewater treatment leads to its accumulation. IBU can adversely affect microbial communities and aquatic organisms, contributing to ecological imbalances [12,40]. SMX is often detected in both treated and untreated wastewater. It contributes to the growing issue of antimicrobial resistance, as its presence in the environment can promote the proliferation of resistant bacteria. Additionally, SMX has been shown to exert toxic effects on aquatic organisms, even at low concentrations [41]. The last analyzed PhCs is carbamazepine – a widely prescribed anticonvulsant, known for its high chemical stability and resistance to degradation. It is a persistent contaminant frequently detected in surface and groundwater and remains largely unaffected by conventional treatment processes. CBZ's persistence raises concerns about its long-term environmental accumulation and potential for chronic toxicity in aquatic systems [17,42,43]. These substances represent different therapeutic classes and possess diverse chemical structures and biological activities, comprehensively assessing the efficacy of the Fenton and photo-Fenton processes. Moreover, DCF, SMX, and CBZ have repeatedly shown NR in conventional processes; therefore, particular attention should be paid to the search for effective processes to remove these substances. The research focuses on several key parameters that influence the efficiency of the Fenton and photo-Fenton reactions, including pH, dose of H_2O_2 , exposure time, and the concentration ratios of the reagents (Fe^{2+}). Understanding how these factors affect the degradation process is crucial for optimizing treatment conditions and maximizing the removal efficiency of PhCs from aqueous solutions. The novelty of this study lies in the

simultaneous removal of PhCs from different therapeutic groups (IBU, DCF, CBZ, and SMX) while optimizing the parameters of the Fenton and photo-Fenton processes. This approach addresses a significant knowledge gap regarding the potential application of these methods and their modifications for concurrently removing multiple compounds under the most efficient and optimized conditions. In addition to the traditional Fenton and photo-Fenton processes, our study explores the innovative use of two different iron-based NPs as catalysts instead of conventional iron (II) sulfate. This novel approach leverages the unique properties of NPs, such as their high surface area and enhanced catalytic activity, to improve the degradation of various pharmaceutical contaminants.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

All PhCs used in the analysis were characterized by high purity: diclofenac sodium salt (purity $\geq 98\%$, TLC, Sigma-Aldrich), ibuprofen sodium salt (purity $\geq 98\%$, GC, Sigma-Aldrich), sulfamethoxazole (GC, HPLC, Sigma-Aldrich) and carbamazepine (purity $\geq 97.0\%$, Glentham). Reagents such as ethanol ($\geq 99.9\%$), ultra-pure water (for HPLC), acetonitrile ($\geq 99.9\%$), phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4), iron (II) sulfate heptahydrate ($\text{FeSO}_4 \times 7 \text{H}_2\text{O}$), hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) were purchased at Sigma-Aldrich. The stock solution was prepared by dissolving 250 mg of each of the four PhCs in 10 mL of ethanol using a magnetic stirrer, resulting in a 25 mg/mL concentration for each PhC. The stock solution was stored at 4 degrees Celsius. The research used a working solution with a concentration of 25 mg/L of each pharmaceutical obtained by diluting the stock solution a thousand times with ultrapure water. The pH of each sample was measured using a portable multiparameter meter. In turn, zero-valent iron nanoparticles were purchased at 3D-nano. The descriptions of the NPs used in the study are presented in Table 1.

2.2. Fenton and photo-Fenton process – research scheme

The research was conducted in six stages, and their scheme is presented in Fig. 1. In the first and second stages, the influence of pH and hydrogen peroxide dose on the efficiency of pharmaceutical removal was determined, with iron (II) sulfate as the source and the process being carried out at an $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ ratio of 10. In the subsequent research stages, the influence of the H_2O_2 to iron ratio on the efficiency of pharmaceutical removal was assessed, with the focus on determining how the use of photo-Fenton or another iron source would affect the efficiency of the process in comparison to the classic Fenton reaction conducted with iron (II) sulfate. For this reason, studies using photo-Fenton and iron nanoparticles were carried out at higher molar ratios of hydrogen peroxide and iron, assuming that their use would improve the process's efficiency while reducing reagents.

The Fenton and photo-Fenton processes were carried out under standard conditions to evaluate the removal efficiency of the selected contaminants. The Fenton process was conducted in a glass reactor,

Table 1
Description of nanoparticles used in Fenton processes.

	Nanoparticle A	Nanoparticle B
Substance	Iron (Fe)	Iron (Fe) - Carbon Coated
Particle size [nm]	22	22
Purity [%]	99.55	99.55
Crystal Structure	cubic	cubic
Specific surface area [m^2/g]	45 –65	45 –65
Bulk density [g/mL]	7.9	7.9
Additional information	partially passivated	partially passivated by coating nanoparticles with 8,7 wt% carbon

Fig. 1. Scheme of the experiment.

while the photo-Fenton process was carried out using the Laboratory UV Reactor System 3 (UV-Consulting Peschl). This system includes UV immersion lamps TNN 15/32, an immersion tube, and a reactor vessel. The UV immersion lamp is a low-pressure mercury lamp emitting at a wavelength of 253.4 nm. The experiments were carried out at 20 ± 1 °C.

500 mL of working solution was used in each process, and the experiments were performed for 60 min. In the first 30 min, samples were taken every 5 min, and the last one was taken 60 min after the start of the process. The only exception to this rule was used in the first stage of the study, in which the effect of pH on the efficiency of the process was assessed. In this case, the process was carried out in 200 mL, and samples for analysis were taken after 30 and 60 min. To determine the efficiency of the process in the given time intervals, immediately after taking the samples, their pH was raised to 10 using 0.3 M NaOH. Immediately before the chromatographic analysis, the pH of the sample was again corrected to 3.0 using 0.1 M sulfuric acid. After this treatment, the samples were filtered through a 0.35 μm syringe filter.

2.3. Chromatographic analysis

After the Fenton and photo-Fenton processes, the content of PhCs was determined using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) coupled with a UV-VIS diode array detector (DAD). A reversed-phase analytical column Accucore™ C18 (2.6 μm , 150 mm \times 3 mm) was used for HPLC. The software used in the study is Chromeleon™ Chromatography Data System (CDS) Software.

Chromatographic conditions are modifications of Gilart's process [44] Table 2 shows the basic parameters of HPLC-DAD conditions. Fig. 1 shows the experiment's scheme.

Table 2
Chromatographic conditions.

Parameters	Chromatographic conditions
Flow rate	0.6 mL/min
Temperature	40 degrees Celsius
Wavelength	230 nm
Solvents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ultra-pure water acidified to pH 2.8 by H_3PO_4 (solvent A) acetonitrile (solvent B)
Time	21 min

2.4. Statistical analysis

The removal efficiency (RE) of diclofenac, ibuprofen, carbamazepine, and sulfamethoxazole was determined using the following Eq. (5):

$$\text{RE}(\%) = \frac{(C_0 - C_t) \times 100}{C_0} \quad (5)$$

where C_0 is the initial concentration of PhC compound; C_t is the concentration of PhCs at the time. Additionally, a factorial analysis of variance was performed to determine how selected factors influence the process efficiency. Statistical analyses were performed in Excel (version 365) and STATISTICA.

3. Results & discussions

3.1. Impact of initial pH on pharmaceuticals removal efficiency

In the first stage, the effect of initial pH on the efficiency of the Fenton process for removing PhCs was determined. The experiment was conducted for pH values of 2, 2.5, 3, 3.5, 4, 4.5. The results are presented

Fig. 2. The effect of pH on the removal efficiency of a) sulfamethoxazole; b) carbamazepine; c) diclofenac; d) ibuprofen; experiment condition: 0.24 mL/L H_2O_2 ; $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{Fe}^{2+}$ equal 10.

in Fig. 2. After 30 min, the highest RE for SMX and DCF occurs at pH 2.5, with removal rates of 86.06 % and 91.35 %, respectively. IBU shows the highest removal at pH 2 with a rate of 90.70 %, and CBZ's highest RE occurs at pH 3.0. After 60 min, the optimal pH for SMX and DCF remains at 2.5. Despite the described scatter of results, except for diclofenac, statistical analysis did not show a statistically significant effect of initial pH on PhCs removal efficiency. Moreover, for samples with pH higher than 2.5, after 30 min, the index decreased to the level of 2.52 ± 0.03 (average for samples with pH from 2.5 to 4.5), which is the effect of the formation of sulphate ions as a result of iron sulphate dissociation. Due to the lack of statistical differences between the initial pH of the solution, further studies were conducted at pH 3. The choice of this range was primarily determined by the mechanism of the Fenton process because although at low pH, hydrogen peroxide is more stable and decomposes more slowly to form hydroxyl radicals, a very low pH favours

the reaction of radicals with an excess of hydrogen ions, which in turn may result in a decrease in the efficiency of the process [45–51]. On the other hand, if the initial pH is too high, hydrogen ions are used up too quickly, which increases the solution pH, leading to the precipitation of iron in the form of hydroxides. In addition, high pH promotes the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide into water and oxygen, which causes it to lose its oxidizing properties, which reduces the efficiency of the redox reaction and, in the long run, the efficiency of the decomposition of organic pollutants.

3.2. Impact of hydrogen peroxide dose on pharmaceutical removal efficiency

Hydrogen peroxide is a source of hydroxyl radicals in the Fenton reaction; therefore, determining its optimal dose is one of the key

parameters. Too high a dose not only does not translate into improved process efficiency but also results in its inadequate use as a result of radical scavenging or compound decomposition according to the following reactions [52,53]:

In addition, excessive levels of H_2O_2 can reduce the process's efficiency and translate into higher operating costs for the solution. Furthermore, the reagent used in excess cannot be recovered in any way [46,54]. Moreover, its potentially toxic effects must be eliminated

before the final effluent is discharged into water bodies [53].

For this reason, in the second study stage, the impact of H_2O_2 dosage on the removal efficiency of PhCs was examined (Fig. 3). The analysis using an $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{Fe}^{2+}$ ratio of 10:1, with varying dosages of H_2O_2 : 1.2, 2.4, 3.6, 4.8, 6.0, and 7.3 mL (all per litre). The results confirmed that the RE of all PhCs statistically significantly increases with the increase in H_2O_2 dosage ($p < 0.05$). For DCF, this difference was the smallest; even at a low H_2O_2 volume of 1.2 mL/L, 80.56 % of the compound was removed within the first 5 min of the process.

Based on the obtained results, further studies were conducted using a constant dose of hydrogen peroxide of 7.3 mL/L. This dose was selected based on the highest process efficiency and the estimated theoretical dose of hydrogen peroxide needed for the mineralization of organic

Fig. 3. The effect of hydrogen peroxide dose on the removal efficiency of a) sulfamethoxazole; b) carbamazepine; c) diclofenac; and d) ibuprofen.

matter in the model solution (estimated based on the formula given in the work of Li et al. [48]).

The literature is full of examples of conducting Fenton reactions at much higher doses of H₂O₂. For instance, CBZ and IBU by Sun et al. [55, 56] were removed at a 600 mM dose of hydrogen peroxide, while Ribeiro et al. [57] degraded SMX at 500 mM H₂O₂.

3.3. Impact of hydrogen peroxide to iron ratio (H₂O₂:Fe²⁺) on pharmaceutical removal efficiency

Maintaining adequate hydrogen peroxide and iron levels is crucial in the Fenton process. An excess or insufficiency of these substances can significantly diminish the effectiveness of the process [52,54]. Furthermore, utilizing suitable levels of these substances can prevent unnecessary operational expenses arising from their surplus use. Moreover, it can alleviate the challenges of eliminating excess iron to meet

Fig. 4. The effect of hydrogen peroxide to iron ratio on the removal efficiency of a) sulfamethoxazole; b) carbamazepine; c) diclofenac; d) ibuprofen.

effluent standards [53]. It should also be noted that higher concentrations of ferrous ions relative to hydrogen peroxide may stimulate chemical coagulation rather than oxidation of contaminants, leading to increased H_2O_2 consumption and increased sludge production [46]. For this reason, the following research issue analyzed was the effect of the $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{Fe}^{2+}$ ratio on removal efficiency. A wide range of ratios was evaluated because their values ranged from 2 to 100. Analyzing the data presented in Fig. 4, including the results of factorial analysis of variance, it was noted that the $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{Fe}^{2+}$ ratio has the most significant impact on the efficiency of removal of all pharmaceuticals, to a lesser extent, the reaction time and to the least extent the interaction of the mentioned factors. 100 % removal of compounds was noted only for SMX, CBZ, and IBU when the ratio values were lower than 25. In the case of higher ratios, achieving pharmaceutical REs above 80 % required a more prolonged process duration, exceeding 25 min. In turn, DCF was not completely decomposed in any of the tests, only to a level of ninety-something percent. However, for ratios higher than 20, over 80 % of its removal was noted earlier, as early as the 20th minute. It is also worth noting that in the case of this compound, the addition of hydrogen peroxide alone brought very positive results, as after 15 min, the efficiency of DCF removal was higher than 70 %. The fact that hydrogen peroxide decomposes diclofenac more effectively than carbamazepine, sulfamethoxazole, and ibuprofen should be associated with its chemical structure. Two aromatic rings and chlorine atoms in the chemical structure of DCF make it more susceptible to oxidation, as they facilitate many oxidation paths and the rapid attack of hydroxyl radicals produced from H_2O_2 . In contrast, the stable tricyclic structure of carbamazepine, the less reactive sulfonamide group of sulfamethoxazole, and the simpler aromatic ring with an alkyl side chain of ibuprofen make them less susceptible to the action of H_2O_2 , resulting in slower and less efficient degradation [58–61].

Although the described research problem has been the subject of numerous studies, new data are still needed due to the matrix, the combination of impurities, and the process conditions. For instance, Rostami et al. [62], in their study on SMX removal, proposed $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{Fe}^{2+}$ ratio (3:2, 7:2, 11:2) and observed that with the increase of $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{Fe}^{2+}$ ratio, the removal efficiency increases from 87 % to 99 %. This trend is opposite to the results obtained in this work however it should be noted that the $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{Fe}^{2+}$ ratios proposed by Rostami et al. [62] are similar to those for which complete SMX removal was observed in this study and do not cover much higher ratios (e.g. 25:1, 50:1, 100:1). In turn, Martínez-Costa et al. [63], in their study on the simultaneous removal of SMX and trimethoprim using Fenton, Fenton-like, and photo-Fenton processes, determined that the crucial parameter in UV-free processes is the Fe^{2+} concentration itself. They observed that a 10-fold increase in Fe^{2+} resulted in an increase in SMX removal from 20.8 % to 99.7 %. This finding aligns with the results of this work, where the best pharmaceutical removal effects were achieved in reactions with a low $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{Fe}^{2+}$ ratio. In the present study, CBZ and IBU behaved similarly to SMX, with removal efficiency significantly higher at lower $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{Fe}^{2+}$ ratios. While Lee et al. [64] in their study analyzed $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{Fe}^{2+}$ ratios of 5:10, 1:1, 2:1, 5:1, 10:1, 20:1, and 50:1. They found that CBZ was almost completely degraded within 30 min at ratios of 5:1 and higher. The higher H_2O_2 concentration led to more efficient CBZ removal due to increased hydroxyl radical generation. These results align with those from the present study, except at the 50:1 ratio, where a decrease in efficiency was observed. This decrease may be related to other pharmaceuticals in the solution. In turn, Abdulrazaq et al. [65], optimizing IBU removal efficiency, proposed $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{Fe}^{2+}$ ratios of 10:1, 30:1, and 50:1. They observed that IBU removal efficiency increased as the $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{Fe}^{2+}$ ratio decreased, although efficiency did not reach 100 %. The IBU removal efficiency found in this work is similar to their results. However, Abdulrazaq et al. did not evaluate lower $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{Fe}^{2+}$ ratios. While Miele et al. [66], in their study on photo-Fenton degradation of DCF, found that optimized conditions without pH control were $\text{Fe}^{2+} = 0.27$ mmol/L and $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 = 1.64$ mmol/min, which resulted in a removal percentage of 93 %. In

contrast, under pH-controlled conditions with a lower $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{Fe}^{2+}$ ratio ($\text{Fe}^{2+} = 1.0$ mmol/L and $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 = 1.64$ mmol/min), the process was less efficient, achieving only 68 %. The results showed that lower concentration of Fe^{2+} without pH control improved degradation. This result indicates that the reagent ratio is not the most critical parameter for DCF removal.

3.4. Impact of reaction type on pharmaceuticals removal efficiency: Fenton vs photo-Fenton processes

In the fourth stage of the study, acidified samples were subjected to the photo-Fenton reaction, which allowed for determining how UV radiation affects the removal efficiency of selected PhCs. The results are presented in Fig. 5. The effectiveness of the Fenton and Photo-Fenton processes in removing SMX, CBZ, DCF, and IBU was assessed through factorial ANOVA analysis results (Table 3). The analysis used the following categorical predictors (factors): reaction type (Fenton vs. Photo-Fenton), the ratio of $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{Fe}^{2+}$, and reaction time. The type of reaction had the most significant influence on the removal of all compounds tested. Moreover, significantly higher values were observed for photo-Fenton. This is not surprising because UV light helps to break down H_2O_2 into hydroxyl radicals and can also photo-reduce Fe^{3+} back to Fe^{2+} , sustaining the production of hydroxyl radicals [46,58,67–69].

The highest F-value (453.29) with a p-value of less than 0.01 was recorded for SMX. Related results were noted in the literature, where UV radiation increased the SMX removal efficiency [30]. For CBZ and IBU, the reaction type played a crucial role, with F-values of 223.35 and 203.97, respectively, and p-values less than 0.01. Only for DCF did the reaction type show a marginally significant effect, with an F-value of 4.04 and a p-value of 0.05, indicating a slight impact on degradation. Overall, the Photo-Fenton process demonstrated superior performance compared to the Fenton process, especially for SMX, CBZ, and IBU. These results confirm the general trend observed in the literature [69–71], indicating that combining the Fenton process with UV radiation significantly enhances the efficiency of removing individual pharmaceuticals and is much more effective for simultaneously removing multiple compounds. This improvement is crucial and suggests promising potential for broader application of this method.

3.5. Impact of different source of iron on pharmaceuticals removal efficiency

Zero valent iron nanoparticles (ZVI NPs) enhance the Fenton reaction by acting as catalysts that facilitate the reduction of hydrogen peroxide to produce hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$), which are highly reactive and degrade organic pollutants. Their nanoscale size provides a high surface area, increasing reactivity and interaction with hydrogen peroxide. Moreover, ZVI NPs also serve as a source of electrons for reducing Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} , ensuring continuous hydroxyl radical production. This combination accelerates reaction rates and creates synergistic effects, making the Fenton process more efficient and effective in breaking down contaminants [72,73]. For these reasons, a comparative analysis utilizing obtained results for $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, iron nanoparticles, and carbon-coated iron nanoparticles was conducted to assess the impact of different iron sources on pharmaceutical RE. Results are shown in Fig. 6a, Fig. 6b and Table 4. For all PhCs, the source of iron had a highly significant impact on their RE, with F-values ranging from 29.23 to 1316.70 and p-values of 0.00, indicating that the choice of iron source plays a crucial role in the effectiveness of the process. At lower ratios of H_2O_2 to Fe^{2+} (10:1, 20:1), removal efficiency approaches nearly 100 % for all PhCs when using $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. In contrast, the iron nanoparticles exhibit reduced effectiveness at these ratios. However, at higher ratios (25:1, 50:1, 75:1), the efficiency of reactions utilizing $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ decreases and becomes comparable to that achieved with iron nanoparticles. Generally, better results were obtained for nanoparticles B (Iron (Fe) - Carbon Coated). Apart from carbon, other materials are used

Fig. 5. a Reaction type: Fenton (PF) vs. photo-Fenton (FF) process - influence on the efficiency of removal of sulfamethoxazole and carbamazepine b Reaction type: Fenton (PF) vs. photo-Fenton (FF) process - influence on the efficiency of removal of diclofenac and ibuprofen.

Fig. 5. (continued).

Table 3
Results of factorial variance conducted for the Fenton (PF) and photo-Fenton (FF) processes.

	Sulfamethoxazole		Carbamazepine		Diclofenac		Ibuprofen	
	F	p	F	P	F	P	F	p
Reaction type	453.29	0.00	223.35	0.00	4.04	0.05	203.97	0.00
Ratio H ₂ O ₂ /Fe ²⁺	62.79	0.00	38.95	0.00	6.18	0.00	32.58	0.00
Time	43.36	0.00	31.37	0.00	12.12	0.00	32.86	0.00
Reaction type × Ratio H ₂ O ₂ /Fe ²⁺	50.54	0.00	28.42	0.00	2.77	0.02	31.11	0.00
Reaction type × Time	11.68	0.00	5.59	0.00	0.58	0.77	6.60	0.00
Ratio H ₂ O ₂ /Fe ²⁺ × Time	4.64	0.00	3.98	0.00	1.23	0.20	3.70	0.00
Reaction type × Ratio H ₂ O ₂ /Fe ²⁺ × Time	2.63	0.00	1.55	0.04	0.84	0.72	1.62	0.02

Reaction type: PF (Fenton process) and FF (Photo-Fenton process)

as the support material, e.g., zeolites, which improve the stability of FeO in suspensions and during transport [74]. It is difficult to compare the obtained results with literature data because the removal efficiency depends to a significant extent on the properties of the pharmaceutical and the structure of the catalyst [75]. The situation is additionally complicated because various modifications are often used to remove organic compounds using FeO as a catalyst, which allows for changing the catalyst's surface, accelerating iron corrosion consequently leading to improved process efficiency. For example, in this goal, the UD field [76], a magnetic field with the addition of EDTA [77], was used to remove DCF. This study removed SMX, CBZ, DCF, and IBU. This study removed SMX, CBZ, DCF, and IBU for optimal conditions with the efficiency of 86 %, 86 %, 91 % and 82 %, respectively. Compared to the literature data, these are slightly lower values. It is worth emphasizing, however, that other authors obtained these results with a much longer reaction time. For example, DCF, in the study [77] was decomposed entirely (Fe⁰ = 0.4 g/L, plus EDTA addition two mM/L, 120 min, C₀ = 10 mg/L). In true, in the work [78], the efficiency of DCF removal ranged from 73.6 to 92.5 % (S-FeO, plus oxygen aeration 800 mL/min, reaction time 120 min, co = 10 mg/L). In turn [79] noted 88 % removal of IBU, but the reaction time in this case was 180 min and the Fe-zeolite dose was at the level of 4.8 g/L (C₀ = 20 mg/L), and [80] achieved 100 % removal of the compound, but this required the use of Fe-graphite (5 mg/l) and the action of the UD field (reaction time 60 min, C₀ = 10 mg/L).

3.6. Fenton processes: opportunities, challenges, and economic considerations

Fenton and photo-Fenton processes are recognized for their efficiency in degrading a wide range of pharmaceuticals from aqueous solutions. These methods offer significant advantages (Table 5), including high degradation rates, simplicity, and the ability to operate under mild conditions. However, several challenges and considerations must be addressed to advance their practical application. One key challenge is the potential formation of intermediate by-products during the degradation process [81–85]. While often less harmful than the parent compounds, these by-products can still pose environmental and health risks. For example, previous studies have identified transformation products that exhibit higher toxicity or persistence, underscoring the importance of monitoring these substances [81,86]. Advanced analytical techniques, such as liquid chromatography and high-resolution mass spectrometry, are essential for identifying these intermediates. Furthermore, toxicity assessments using bioassays or computational models can provide insights into the potential risks associated with these degradation products [12,81,87]. While our study focused primarily on the removal efficiency, future research should aim to comprehensively identify these transformation products using advanced analytical techniques such as

mass spectrometry and assess their toxicity through bioassays or computational models. Economic considerations also play a crucial role in determining the feasibility of Fenton-based treatments for large-scale applications. The cost is influenced by factors such as reagent prices, energy consumption, and the need for post-treatment processes [88]. Previous studies have suggested that while these processes are effective in removing pharmaceuticals, their scalability can be limited by the high cost of hydrogen peroxide and the need for pH control [88]. Additionally, energy consumption, especially in photo-Fenton processes, contributes to the overall cost. To address these challenges, recent innovations, such as the use of iron-based nanoparticles and alternative energy sources (e.g., solar UV), have been explored to improve cost-efficiency. Further research on scaling up these processes and developing cost-efficient alternatives will be essential for their practical implementation in wastewater treatment systems. Despite these limitations, the Fenton and photo-Fenton processes hold immense potential for pharmaceutical removal, particularly when optimized for reagent ratios and combined with novel catalysts. Future studies should focus on overcoming the economic barriers, improving process scalability, and addressing environmental concerns related to intermediate by-products.

4. Conclusion

The Fenton reaction and its modifications can successfully remove pharmaceuticals from aqueous solutions, offering significant promise for environmental remediation. Except for DCF removal, pH changes had no statistically significant effect on PhCs removal efficiency. Hydrogen peroxide dosage was crucial, with an optimal dose of 7.3 mL/L enhancing removal efficiency. The H₂O₂:Fe²⁺ ratio significantly affected RE, with lower ratios generally yielding better results. Results of the photo-Fenton process consistently outperformed results obtained during the Fenton process, particularly for SMX, CBZ, and IBU, which showed complete decomposition even after 10 min. As the test results show, the source of iron played a vital role, with FeSO₄·7H₂O providing superior performance compared to iron nanoparticles at lower H₂O₂:Fe²⁺ ratios. However, the results suggest that using zero-valent iron particles (nZVI) at higher ratios and NPs may be a good, non-toxic, and environmentally friendly alternative. These findings provide valuable insights into optimizing AOPs for pharmaceutical removal, emphasizing the importance of reagent ratios, reaction conditions, and catalyst selection. This study confirms the efficacy of the Fenton and photo-Fenton processes and underscores their potential for broader application in wastewater treatment systems. Future research should explore scaling these processes for real-world applications, assessing their performance with complex matrices, and investigating the environmental safety of by-products. Additionally, integrating advanced materials, such as modified iron nanoparticles, could further enhance efficiency and sustainability in pharmaceutical remediation.

Fig. 6. (a) Source of iron - influence on the removal efficiency of sulfamethoxazole and carbamazepine. (b) Source of iron - influence on the removal efficiency of diclofenac and ibuprofen.

Fig. 6. (continued).

Table 4
Results of factorial variance conducted for various sources of iron.

	Sulfamethoxazole		Carbamazepine		Diclofenac		Ibuprofen	
	F	P	F	P	F	p	F	p
Source of iron	1224.10	0.00	1316.70	0.00	29.23	0.00	494.75	0.00
Ratio H ₂ O ₂ /Fe ²⁺	22.07	0.00	9.74	0.00	68.14	0.00	19.35	0.00
Time	46.74	0.00	38.58	0.00	11.14	0.00	36.23	0.00
Source of iron × Ratio H ₂ O ₂ /Fe ²⁺	109.67	0.00	86.88	0.00	37.48	0.00	74.85	0.00
Source of iron × Time	3.46	0.00	2.25	0.01	0.63	0.84	1.15	0.32
Ratio H ₂ O ₂ /Fe ²⁺ × Time	4.41	0.00	3.58	0.00	0.60	0.95	1.80	0.01
Source of iron × Ratio H ₂ O ₂ /Fe ²⁺ × Time	2.16	0.00	1.57	0.01	1.39	0.05	1.54	0.02

Table 5
Advantages, disadvantages and future perspective of Fenton processes.

Category	Advantages	Disadvantages	Future Perspectives
Fenton Process	- High efficiency for organic pollutant degradation. - Simple operation and widely studied.	- Limited to acidic conditions (optimal pH ~3). - High sludge production and disposal challenges.	- Explore sustainable sludge management methods. - Develop more robust catalysts to expand pH usability.
Photo-Fenton Process	- Enhanced removal efficiency with UV/light. - Capable of degrading persistent pollutants.	- High energy consumption. - Limited outdoor application due to dependency on UV intensity.	- Use renewable energy sources. - Investigate the use of visible-light catalysts for broader applicability.
Modified Fenton, eg. with NPs	- Use of nanocatalysts improves degradation rates. - Potential for pH flexibility.	- High production costs for nanomaterials. - Potential environmental impact of nanoparticles.	- Develop cost-effective and eco-friendly nanomaterials. - Investigate recyclability and recovery of catalysts.
Cost Considerations	- Low chemical cost compared to other advanced oxidation processes. - Scalable for industrial use.	- Operating costs increase with reagent dosage. - High cost of energy for photo-Fenton processes.	- Conduct life-cycle assessments. - Optimize reagent ratios to balance cost and efficiency.

Abbreviations

Advanced oxidation process	AOP
Carbamazepine	CBZ
Diclofenac	DCF
Emerging contaminants	EC
High-performance liquid chromatography	HPLC
Ibuprofen	IBU
Nanoparticle	NP
Pharmaceuticals	PhCs
Removal efficiency	RE
Sulfamethoxazole	SMX
Wastewater treatment plants	WWTPs
Zero-valent iron particles	nZVI

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Anna Grosser: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Julia Dziubińska:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Anna Grobelak:** Supervision, Project administration. **Klaudia Catus-Makowska:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis,

Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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